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Outlier-Resistant Predictive Modeling For Student Performances In Mathematics: Integrating Mm-Estimation And Lasso Regularization

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ABSTRACT

This study addresses the persistent decline in mathematics performance among Nigerian secondary school students by developing a robust predictive model that is resistant to outliers. Traditional logistic regression models are often compromised by outliers and multicollinearity, leading to biased estimates. To overcome these limitations, this research integrates MM-estimation, which uses Huber's loss function to provide robustness against outliers, with LASSO regularization for feature selection and handling multicollinearity. Using a dataset of 100 students from Bauchi State, Nigeria, supplemented with simulated data (n=100, 300, 600) at 15% and 20% outlier contamination levels, the performance of the proposed integrated model was compared against traditional logistic regression. The results identified Cognitive Score as the most significant predictor of math performance, with School Resources showing marginal significance. The Robust MM-Estimation model demonstrated superior stability and accuracy on real-world data, evidenced by lower AIC (6.10 vs. 6.20), BIC (9.087 vs. 9.187), and error metrics (MAE: 0.100 vs. 0.200). While simulated data showed identical performance for both models, the analysis of real data confirmed the utility of the robust approach in the presence of influential observations. The study concludes that the integration of MM-estimation and LASSO regularization offers a more reliable and interpretable framework for identifying key determinants of academic success in educational datasets prone to outliers.

Keywords: Mathematics Performance, Predictive Modeling, Robust Regression, MM-Estimation, LASSO Regularization, Outlier Resistance, Logistic Regression

INTRODUCTION

As a result, mathematics is one of the most important fundamental disciplines taken into consideration. Because of this, mathematics is one of the most important fundamental disciplines that are included in a school curriculum. Many contend that more mathematics lessons than any other topic may be taught in universities and classrooms across the globe (Suratman *et al.*, 2022).

Compared to the numerous non-formal and informal ways of socialization, education refers to the discipline that is concerned with techniques teaching and learning in schools or school-like situations. It can be viewed as the dissemination of a society's values and body of knowledge. The purpose of education is to help them learn about a culture that will shape their behavior into that of an adult and point them in the direction of their future social role. It is a crucial instrument that comes in quite handy for everyone. The key to success and what sets humans apart from other species on Earth is education. (Vijayalakshmi, 2023). Education also includes mathematics. A historical subject is mathematics. Since ancient times, it has been studied by numerous mathematicians worldwide. The father of mathematics is thought to have been Archimedes, who lived in the BC century. He presented formulas for figuring out a solid's volume and surface area. On the other hand, Aryabhata, who is regarded as the founder of Indian mathematics and was born in 476 CE, derived the word "mathema" from the Greek, meaning "subject of instruction." The study of mathematics involves the use of numbers, forms, quantity, logic, and order. Mathematical branches, symbols, attributes, rules, and formulas are all involved. It teaches how to isolate problems and solve them using mathematical calculations. Additionally, two types of mathematics were described: applied mathematics and pure mathematics. (Sharatk, 2023).

Currently, mathematics is employed as a fundamental building block in every field, including natural science, engineering, medical, and social science, all over the world. As I've already said, mathematics is a modern science and a crucial component of education. The challenges that students encounter in learning mathematics are primarily related to high school. The goal of the word was to look into the variables that affect arithmetic learning. The way that teachers and students view mathematics, the way that students approach learning mathematics, and the degree of difficulty in the mathematical content area are the determining variables. Learners have focused a lot of attention on the attitude of the learner toward mathematics from the influencing variables of attitude toward mathematics. The degree to which a student, instructor, or school has met their immediate or long-term learning objectives is known as their academic performance. The majority of the time, external examinations such as the Basic Education Certificate Examination (BECE), Senior School Certificate Examination (SSCE), and National Examination Council (NECO) administered in Nigeria are used to gauge a student's academic performance. These tests are typically created by teachers or standardized. However, environmental factors like student characteristics, factors linked to the home, and factors associated to the school may have an impact on pupils' academic achievement in mathematics. In the same line, it was mentioned that psychologists have discovered three main categories of factors that affect academic performance: student traits, home environment, and school context (Wahab, 2020). The academic success of students in mathematics is crucial in generating the highest caliber graduates who will be valuable assets to the nation and drive its social and economic advancements. Numerous investigations have been conducted to determine the elements influencing students' academic achievement at numerous educational establishments across the globe. The majority of this research concentrate on three main areas of inquiry: students' personal variables, teachers' academic causal factors, and parents' family causal factors. However, the combination of these variables affecting academic performance differs across different academic environments, student populations, and cultural contexts ((Olowu *et.al* 2020)

According to Lapite *et al.* (2022), Nigerian secondary school students' academic performance in mathematics has been steadily declining over time. This may have made it more difficult for them to meet the requirements for admission to the nation's colleges of education, universities, and polytechnics. Based on the aforementioned, this study aims to investigate the factors that affect secondary school students' performance in mathematics in Bauchi State, Nigeria, including classroom size, gender, parents' socioeconomic status, parental involvement, and self- confidence, as well as the factors that affect teachers' qualifications, competence, interest, years of teaching experience, and teaching resources using robust logistic regression.

Researchers for decades contributed significantly in investigating performance in mathematics using different tools and methodologies, for example Raul (2023) worked on predictor variables of mathematic success in mathematic using binary logistic regression where he considered three factors namely;

affective domain, mathematical processes and pedagogical factors which he found out that affective domain and mathematical processes affect the performance of mathematics.

Similarly, Clement (2023) worked on exploring student and teacher factors influencing student's performance in mathematics using probit regression and he found out that teacher predisposing factors such as subject knowledge and teaching experience have a significant effect on student performance. The method and environment within which students learn mathematics has a significant effect on their performance in the subject, hence effective learning methods and environment would improve their performance in the subject.

Koushik Paul *et al.* (2022) in their study, focused on using multiple logistic regression to predict placement results and they found out that the model showed a high level of prediction accuracy and hereby proposed to be used predict placement results of students' performance performance in mathematics and test anxiety, academic self-concept and motivation.

Taiwo *et al.* (2023) also focused on the predictors of mathematics achievements of secondary school students using multiple regression and it was found out that factors such as parental education and socioeconomic background had no significant relationship with the students' academic achievement.

Oginni *et al.* (2023) concentrated on Metacognitive Ability as Determinant of Senior Secondary School Students Academic Performance in Mathematics and it was found out that metacognitive ability does not influence the performance of mathematics among secondary school students

Oginni (2021) investigated the comparative analysis of psychosocial factors and student's performance in Mathematics among secondary school students and was found out that parental has significant influence on students' academic performance in Mathematics.

Olayinka (2023) worked on the factors influencing the attitudes of secondary school students toward the study of mathematics and it was found out that students have a negative attitude towards the mathematics and this has influenced teachers' methods and parents' views.

Recently, Byiringiro (2024) researched on factors Influencing the Attitude of Students Towards the Study of Mathematics among Secondary Schools using descriptive statistics, correlation and regression analysis and he found out that that teaching approach in teaching mathematics affects students' attitude toward the subject, as the methods and activities used by the teacher reflect attention to learners' experience, also the teacher attitude towards Mathematics is significantly related to high achievement in students, Teachers' instructional methods and activities reflect attention to issues of access, equity and diversity for learners.

Statement of the Problem

Mathematics performance in Nigerian secondary schools has persistently declined, posing significant challenges to educational outcomes. While studies like Raul (2023) have used logistic regression to identify predictors variables of mathematic success, traditional logistic regression remain sensitive to outliers and multicollinearity leading to bias estimates and unreliable predictions. However, existing robust techniques partially address outliers but lack efficiency in high-dimensional data and fail to perform automatic feature selection. Crucially, no study has integrated MM-estimation leveraging Huber's loss function with LASSO regularization to simultaneously handle outliers, multicollinearity and predictors selection. Therefore, this study tends to improve on the existing literatures by integrating the MM-estimation and LASSO model in identifying robust predictors of mathematics performance while resisting outliers' contamination for accurate interpretable models.

Aim and Objectives

The aim of this research is to develop an outlier-resistant predictive model for mathematics performance using integrated MM-estimation (Huber's loss) and LASSO regularization, to enhance accuracy, stability and interpretability. The specific objectives of this research are:

- I. To compare the predictive accuracy of Traditional Logistic Regression and Robust MM-Estimation in classifying student math performance.
- II. To evaluate the impact of outliers on model stability and coefficient estimates.
- III. To identify key predictors of math performance and assess their robustness across modeling approaches.

- IV. To determine the utility of robust methods in educational datasets with varying sample sizes and contamination levels.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study employs a quantitative, correlational, and cross-sectional research design. This approach is deemed appropriate for examining the relationships between various independent variables and the binary outcome of mathematics performance.

Population

The target population is secondary school students of SS1 within in Yelwa Metropolis Bauchi Local Government Area, Bauchi State.

Sample size and Sampling technique

The sample size of 100 students was used for this research from five different secondary schools and also, a stratified random sampling technique will be used to ensure a representative sample of students from various schools.

Data and Variable Descriptions

The data for the study was generated through experimental survey of a sample of 100 students of SS1 that includes boys and girls and a simulated data of sample sizes 100, 300 and 600, with 15% and 20% outliers' contamination to compare the efficacy of the two models in the presence of outliers under different sample sizes scenario. The variables for the study are prescribed and encoded as:

Variables Included

- I. Math Performance: Binary outcome (0 = Fail, 1 = Pass).
- II. Cognitive Score: Continuous (0–100, with outliers).
- III. Socioeconomic Status (SES): Categorical (Low, Medium, High).
- IV. Teacher Experience: Continuous (years of teaching).
- V. Parental Involvement: Ordinal (1–5 scale, 5 = high involvement).
- VI. School Resources: Continuous (funding per student in \$).
- VII. Professional Development: Continuous (training hours/year)

LASSO and Elastic Net Regularization

Regularization techniques like LASSO (Least Absolute Shrinkage and Selection Operator) and Elastic Net are widely used in regression models to prevent overfitting, handle multicollinearity, and improve interpretability by performing automatic feature selection. These methods are especially valuable in high-dimensional datasets (where predictors pp exceed observations nn) or when predictors are correlated.

Concept and Mathematical Formulation

LASSO Regression

LASSO adds an $L1L1$ -penalty to the regression model, which shrinks some coefficients to exactly zero, effectively removing less important predictors.

Objective Function:

$$\min_{\beta} \left\{ \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \beta_0 - \sum_{j=1}^p \beta_j x_{ij})^2 + \lambda \sum_{j=1}^p |\beta_j| \right\} \quad (1)$$

- λ : Tuning parameter controlling shrinkage strength.
- Key Property: Produces sparse models (feature selection)

Elastic Net Regression

Elastic Net combines $L1L1$ (LASSO) and $L2L2$ (Ridge) penalties to balance feature selection and group correlation handling.

Objective Function:

$$\min_{\beta} \left\{ \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \beta_0 - \sum_{j=1}^p \beta_j x_{ij})^2 + \lambda \left(\alpha \sum_{j=1}^p |\beta_j| + \frac{1-\alpha}{2} \sum_{j=1}^p \beta_j^2 \right) \right\} \quad (2)$$

α : Mixing parameter ($\alpha = 1$: LASSO; $\alpha = 0$: Ridge).

Advantages:

Retains LASSO’s sparsity while handling correlated predictors (unlike pure LASSO).

More stable than LASSO when $p \gg n$.

Logistic regression

Logistic regression is a statistical method that is used to determine a relationship between one dependent variable and one or more explanatory variables where the dependent variable has a binary outcome (K Gosh 2024). A sigmoid curve is used in logistic regression to illustrate the relationship between the independent variables and the target. Logistic regression is mostly applied if your dependent variable Y has a discrete value. In other words, it has two values either 0 or 1, true or false, pass or fail. Logistic function is used in logistic regression to measure the relationship between the target variable and independent variable. Below is the equation that denotes the logistic regression

$$\text{Logit } P = \ln \left(\frac{p}{1-p} \right)$$

Where p is the probability of occurrence of the feature.

Key assumptions for implementing logistic regression

For logistic regression to be used, it is highly imperative that these assumptions are fully obeyed

- i. The dependent or response variable is binary or dichotomous
- ii. Little or no multicollinearity between the predictor/explanatory variables
- iii. Linear relationship of independent variable to log odds
- iv. There should be sufficient large sample size
- v. No extreme outliers
- vi. The observation in the dataset should be independent of each other.

Robust Logistic Regression

Robust logistic regression is a statistical technique that aims to improve the accuracy and reliability of logistic regression models when dealing with datasets that contain outliers or influential observations. Outliers and influential observations can significantly impact the results of traditional logistic regression, leading to biased estimates and unreliable predictions. Robust logistic regression seeks to increase the precision and dependability of logistic regression models while working with datasets that include significant observations or outliers. Traditional logistic regression findings can be greatly impacted by outliers and noteworthy data, which can result in skewed estimates and inaccurate forecasts.

Robust MM-estimator

Robust MM estimator procedure is to estimate the regression parameter using S estimator which minimize the scale of the residual from S estimation and then proceed with M estimator. MM estimation aims to obtain estimates that have a high breakdown value and more efficient. Breakdown value is a common measure of the proportion of outliers that can be addressed before these observations affect the model.

M- Estimation

One of the robust regression estimation methods is the M estimation. The letter M indicates that M-estimation is an estimation of the maximum likelihood type.

If estimator at M-estimation is $\hat{\beta} = \beta_n(x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_n) - - - - 1$ then

$$E[\beta_n(x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_n)] = \beta$$

Equation (1) shows that the estimator $\hat{\beta} = \beta_n(x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_n)$ is unbiased and has minimum variance, so M-estimator has the smallest variance estimator compared to other estimators of variance:

$$var(\hat{\beta}) \geq \frac{[\beta]^2}{nE\left(\frac{d}{d\beta} \ln f(x_i; \beta)\right)^2} \quad (3)$$

Where $\tilde{\beta}$ is other linear and unbiased estimator for β . M estimation is an extension of the maximum likelihood estimate method and a robust estimation. M estimation principle is to minimize the residual function ρ . Dalalyan and Thompson (2019); Deng et al, 2014; Susanti et al 2014

Algorithm 1: M - Estimator

1. Estimate regression coefficients on the data using OLS.
2. Test assumptions of the regression model
3. Detect the presence of outliers in the data.
4. Calculate estimated parameter β_0 with OLS.
5. Calculate residual value $e_i = y_i - \hat{y}_i$
6. Calculate value $\hat{\sigma}_i = 1.4826 MAD$
7. Calculate value $u_i = e_i / \hat{\sigma}_i$
8. Calculate the weighted value using: $w_i = \begin{cases} \left[1 - \left(\frac{u_i}{4.685}\right)^2\right]^2 & ; |u_i| \leq 4.685 \\ 0 & ; |u_i| > 4.685 \end{cases} \quad (4)$
9. Calculate $\hat{\beta}_M$ using weighted least squares (WLS) method with weighted w_i
10. Repeat steps 5-8 to obtain a convergent value of $\hat{\beta}_M$ and test to determine whether independent variables have significant effect on the dependent variable.

MM-Estimator Algorithm

The Goal of the MM-estimator Algorithm is to estimate the regression coefficients $\hat{\beta}_{MM}$ that are both robust to outliers and efficient under normality.

1. Initial S-Estimation (High Breakdown Point)

- Objective: Find an initial robust estimate $\hat{\beta}_S$ using an S-estimator.
- Steps:
 1. Define a robust scale estimator $s(r)$ (e.g., Tukey’s biweight) of the residuals

$$r_i = y_i - x_i^T \beta$$

2. Solve: $\hat{\beta}_S = \arg \min_{\beta} s(y - X\beta)$

Typically, this is done using a fast algorithm like Fast-S (Rousseeuw and Yohai, 1984).

3. Compute residuals $r_i = y_i - x_i^T \hat{\beta}_s$ and their robust scale $\hat{\sigma}_s = s(r)$

2. Refinement via M-Estimation (Efficient Tuning)

- Objective: Improve efficiency by solving an *M-estimation* problem using the initial $\hat{\beta}_s$ and $\hat{\sigma}_s$

- Steps:

1. Choose a loss function $\rho(\cdot)$ (e.g., Tukey's biweight) tuned for efficiency.

2. Solve:
$$\hat{\beta}_{MM} = \arg \min_{\beta} s \sum_{i=1}^n \rho \left(\frac{y_i - x_i^T \beta}{\hat{\sigma}_s} \right)$$

Often solved via Iteratively Reweighted Least Squares (IRLS):

- Compute weights $w_i = \rho' (r_i / \hat{\sigma}_s) / (r_i / \hat{\sigma}_s)$.
- Update β via weighted least squares: $\hat{\beta} = (X^T W T)^{-1} X^T W y$, where $W = \text{diag}(w_i)$

3. Iterate until convergence

Key Properties:

- Breakdown Point: Inherits high breakdown (~50%) from the S-estimator.
- Efficiency: Achieves high asymptotic efficiency (e.g., 95% under normality) via the M-step tuning.
- Robustness: Resistant to outliers in both *y* and *both X*

S - Estimation

The weakness of M-estimation is the lack of consideration on the data distribution and not a function of the overall data because only using the median as the weighted value. This method uses the residual standard deviation to overcome the weaknesses of M- estimator. According to Susanti et al (2014), the S-estimator is defined by $\hat{\beta}_S = \text{Min}_{\beta} \hat{\sigma}_s(e_1, e_2, \dots, e_n)$ with determining minimum robust scale estimator.

Algorithm 2: S - Estimator

1. Estimate regression coefficients on the data using OLS.
2. Test assumptions of the regression model
3. Detect the presence of outliers in the data.
4. Calculate estimated parameter $\hat{\beta}_0$ with OLS.

5. Calculate residual value $e_i = y_i - \hat{y}_i$

6. Calculate value $\hat{\sigma}_i$;

$$\hat{\sigma}_i = \begin{cases} \frac{\text{Median}.e_i.(\text{Median})(e_i)}{0.6745}, & \text{Iteration} = 1 \\ \frac{1}{nK} \sum w_i e_i^2, & \text{Iteration} > 1 \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

7. Calculate the value $u_i = \frac{e_i}{\hat{\sigma}_i}$

8. Calculate the weighted value, w_i

$$w_i = \begin{cases} \left[1 - \left(\frac{u_i}{1.547} \right)^2 \right]^2, & |u_i| \leq 1.547 \quad \text{Iteration} = 1 \\ 0, & |u_i| > 1.547 \\ \frac{\rho(u)}{u^2} & \text{Iteration} > 1 \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

9. Calculate $\hat{\beta}_S$ with WLS method with weighted w_i

10. Repeat steps 5 – 8 to obtain a convergent value of $\hat{\beta}_S$ and test to determine whether independent variables have significant effect on the dependent variable.

MM-Estimation

MM - estimation provide a high breakdown value and more efficient than M and S estimators. Breakdown value is a common measure of the proportion of outliers that can be addressed before these observations affect the model. MM-estimator is the solution of;

$$\sum_{i=1}^n \rho_1(u_i) X_{ij} = 0 \text{ or } \sum_{i=1}^n \rho_1 \left(\frac{Y_i - \sum_{j=0}^k X_{ij} \beta_j}{S_{MM}} \right) X_{ij} = 0 \quad (7)$$

Where S_{MM} is the standard deviation of S estimation and ρ is the Turkey's biweight function defined by:

$$\rho(u_i) = \begin{cases} \frac{u_i^2}{2} - \frac{u_i^4}{2c^2} + \frac{u_i^6}{6c^2}, & -c \leq u_i \leq c \\ \frac{c^2}{6}, & u_i < -c \text{ or } u_i > c \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

Algorithm 3: MM Estimator

1. Estimate regression coefficients on the data using OLS.
2. Test assumptions of the regression model
3. Detect the presence of outliers in the data.
4. Calculate residual value $e_i = y_i - \hat{y}_i$ of S estimate
5. Calculate $\hat{\sigma}_i = \hat{\sigma}_{sn}$

6. Calculate $u_i = \frac{e_i}{\hat{\sigma}_i}$

7. Calculate the weighted value w_i :

$$w_i = \begin{cases} \left[1 - \left(\frac{u_i}{4.685}\right)^2\right]^2, & |u_i| \leq 4.685 \\ 0, & |u_i| > 4.685 \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

8. Calculate $\hat{\beta}_{MM}$ using weighted least square method with weighted w_i

9. Repeat step 5 – 8 to obtain a convergent value of $\hat{\beta}_{MM}$ and test whether the independent variables have a significant effect on the dependent variable.

The MM-estimator for Huber’s Loss Function

Initial S-Estimation (High Breakdown Point)

Objective: Compute an initial robust estimate $\hat{\beta}s$ and scale $\hat{\sigma}s$

1. Huber’s Loss for S-Estimation:

$$\rho_S(r) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{2} r^2 & \text{if } |r| \leq c_M \\ c_S|r| - \frac{1}{2} c_S^2, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

Where $c_s = 1.345$ (default for 95% efficiency under gaussian errors)

2. Solve for $\hat{\beta}s$ and $\hat{\sigma}s$

Minimize the M-scale equation: $\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \rho_S\left(\frac{y_i - x_i^T \hat{\beta}}{\hat{\sigma}_s}\right) = k,$

Where $k = 0.5$ (for consistency)

Use iterative reweighting or Fast-S algorithm.

2.Output: Initial estimates $\hat{\beta}s$ and $\hat{\sigma}s$.

M-Estimation (Efficient Refinement)

Objective: Refine $\hat{\beta}s$ using Huber’s loss tuned for efficiency.

1. Huber’s Loss for M-Estimation:

$$\rho_M(r) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{2} r^2 & \text{if } |r| \leq c_M \\ c_M|r| - \frac{1}{2} c_M^2, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

where $c_M=1.345$ (same as S-step, but can be adjusted).

2. IRLS Algorithm:

- Input: $\hat{\beta}s$ fixed scale $\hat{\sigma}s$

- Iterate until convergence:

1. Compute residuals $r_i = y_i - x_i^T \beta^{(k)}$

2. Compute weights:

- $$\rho_M(r) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } |r| \leq c_M \hat{\sigma}s, \\ \frac{c_M \hat{\sigma}s}{|r|}, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

3. Update $\beta^{(k+1)}$: $\beta^{(k+1)} = \hat{\beta} = (X^T W T)^{-1} X^T W y$, where $W = \text{diag}(w_i)$

Hence the output for the final MM-estimate $\hat{\beta}_{MM}$

Modified Logistic Regression with Huber’s Loss

To modify the Logistic Regression based of Huber’s loss we minimize a robustified version of the logistic loss, replacing the standard log-loss with Huber’s composite loss for outlier resistance.

Huberized Logistic Loss Function

For binary outcomes $y_i \in \{0,1\}$ and predicted probabilities $p_i = \sigma(x_i^T \beta)$ (where σ is the sigmoid),

define: $\ell_{Huber}(y_i, p_i)$

where c is a tuning constant (e.g., $c = 1.345$ $c = 1.345$ for 95% efficiency).

Evaluation Metrics: The model evaluation criterion for the study is;

Model Fit: AIC, BIC, Pseudo R².

Predictive Accuracy: AUC, Sensitivity, Specificity.

Error Metrics: MAE, MSE, RMSE.

Outlier Analysis: Cook’s Distance, Mahalanobis Distance, Studentized Residuals.

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

Descriptive Statistics

Table 1: Dataset Sample (First 10 Rows)

Student ID	Cognitive Score	SES	Teacher Experience	Parental Involvement	School Resources	Professional Development	Math Performance
1	82	Medium	9	4	3200	25	1
2	45	Low	6	2	1800	12	0
3	93	High	14	5	6200	40	1
4	28	Low	5	1	1500	8	0
5	105*	Low	7	3	2000	15	1
6	67	Medium	11	4	3500	28	1
7	19*	High	16	5	6500	45	0
8	88	High	12	5	5800	38	1
9	52	Medium	8	3	3000	20	0
10	115*	Low	4	2	1700	10	1

The data set above in table 1 provides the first 10 values of math performance for 100 students as encoded for the study that highlights several patterns. The results for Students 5, 7 and 10 (all marked with *) seem to be out of the ordinary, considering their scores and backgrounds. Generally, high SES students have access to better materials and usually pass, yet except for Student 7 who did not. Students who come from low-SES environments (2,4,5,10) have a greater range of outcomes and Students 5 and 10 unexpectedly performed well. Having an experienced teacher or being involved does not always help, as it can lead to both good and poor education outcomes (1,3,6,8,7,9). Examining the outliers is necessary, as they could be due to faulty information or showcase how someone can succeed against odds or how someone fails despite being provided all the chances.

Table 2: Student to Teacher Information Descriptive Statistics

Statistic	Student ID	Cognitive Score	SES	Teacher Experience
Min.	1.00	10.00	–	3.00
1st Quartile (Q1)	25.75	52.00	–	8.00
Median	50.50	62.50	–	10.00
Mean	50.50	61.21	–	10.13
3rd Quartile (Q3)	75.25	75.00	–	12.00
Max.	100.00	115.00	–	18.00
Type	Numeric	Numeric	Character	Numeric

Table 2 above shows the important statistics for four variables in relation to the 100 students studied. Individuals might score anywhere from 10 to 115 in Cognitive Scores, with an average of 61.21 and a middle score of 62.5. Teacher Experience is numeric, ranging from 3 to 18 years and the average is 10.13 years (median=10). Because SES is character/categorical, it does not have any descriptive stats and must be analyzed using frequency tables. The number of students in the dataset can be confirmed by the student ID (numeric), starting at 1 and going up to 100. Both the average and median values are so close that the data is unlikely to be skewed, yet the outlier with the highest Cognitive Score (115) should be checked carefully. By breaking down SES further, the group can be clearly shown in comparison to Lower, Middle and Higher count groups.

Outlier and Influence Analysis

Fig 1: Outliers BoxPlot

Fig 1 displays a boxplot that summarizes the four important variables in the dataset, which are Cognitive Score, Teacher Experience, School Resources and Professional Development. CG score is negatively skewed, with the majority scoring well but a few getting scores well below the norm. Most teachers have similar experience, with most values centered at 8 to 12 years.

Meanwhile, School Resources have more diversity and a positive curve, suggesting that the majority of schools are similar, but some have a lot more resources. Teachers generally spend about 21 hours each year on Professional Development, as the distribution is normal with very few exceptions. Regarding variability, there are fewer differences in teacher qualities but more in both students' performances and school resources, suggesting that students may not have equal chances in learning.

Fig 2: Scatterplot Matrix for Continuous Variables

From the scatterplot matrix, we can see that only school Resources is correlated with Cognitive score and that the correlation is statistically significant at 0.655*. Besides Age, all the other variables appear unrelated to SAT scores, as their correlation coefficients are lower than 0.2: Teacher Experience (-0.103), Parental Involvement (-0.068) and school resources with the other variables (0.003-0.037). Most cases of cognitive score fall below 0.02, Teacher Experience is distributed evenly over 5-15 years, the majority of Parental Involvement is under 5 and School resources is seen over a wide range of values. The data imply

that funding for schools is most closely linked to better cognitive scores in this group, while the other factors are not meaningful in their relationships to scores. The use of triple asterisks (***) proves that the relation between School Resources and Cognitive Score is very statistically important ($p < 0.001$).

Fig 3: Variables Diagnosis Plots

Fig 3 presents visualizations that show the key observations and any outliers present in the data sample. Student IDs 9 and 1 have a higher distance than other Students in the Robust Mahalanobis Distance plot. On the plot, we can see that nearly all of the points are close to zero, except for a few moderately influential points around index 20-40. Circle sizes in Challenge Plot point to Cook's distance which means the most common residuals and leverage are close to zero and some bigger circles represent influential cases that ought to be carefully examined to see how they may affect the outcome.

Table 3: Influential Observations Table

Obs. ID	Studentized (StudRes)	Residual	Leverage (Hat)	Cook's (CookD)	Distance	Mahalanobis Distance
7	-2.90		0.082	0.099		-
9	-2.32		0.128	0.108		-
10	-1.49		0.234	0.096		-
75	-3.46		0.056	0.091		-
94	-3.70		0.039	0.069		-
99	+1.51		0.152	0.058		-

Table 3 presents the diagnostic table which shows several important patterns about influential observations and potential outliers in the dataset. The first table identifies six particularly influential cases (Observations 7, 9, 10, 75, 94, and 99) through three key metrics: Studentized Residuals, Leverage, and Cook's Distance. Negative Studentized Residuals (ranging from -1.49 to -3.70) for most cases indicate these observations had actual outcomes substantially lower than what the model predicted, with Observation 94 showing the most extreme underprediction (-3.70). The combination of moderate-to-high Leverage values (particularly Observation 10's 0.234) and substantial Cook's Distance scores (all exceeding the 0.04 threshold) suggests these cases disproportionately influence the model's parameters. Observation 99 stands out as the only case with a positive residual (+1.51), indicating an overprediction, while simultaneously exhibiting high leverage and influence.

Table 4: Mahalanobis Distance Summary

Statistic	Value	Interpretation
Min	0.58	Least extreme observation
1st Quartile	2.15	25% of observations below this
Median	3.94	Central tendency
Mean	5.17	Right-skewed distribution
3rd Quartile	6.43	75% of observations below this
Max	23.68	Most extreme multivariate outlier

Table 4 Presents Mahalanobis Distance summary which provides complementary evidence of multivariate outliers, with a right-skewed distribution (mean of 5.17 versus median of 3.94) and a maximum value of 23.68 that far exceeds the critical χ^2 threshold of 7.38 for two predictors. This indicates several observations lie unusually far from the center of the predictor variable space. The diagnostic thresholds ($|StudRes| > 2.5$, $\hat{Hat} > 0.05$, $CookD > 0.04$) collectively suggest that Observations 94 and 75, despite having lower leverage, warrant special attention due to their extreme residuals and moderate-to-high influence on the model. These patterns imply the robust regression approach was appropriately employed, as conventional methods would be unduly affected by these influential points, particularly given that about 5% of cases exceed multivariate normality expectations.

Fig 4: Mahalanobis Distance Distribution

The histogram in Fig 4 above visualized Mahalanobis distances, which reveals a right-skewed distribution with several notable outliers, indicating the presence of influential observations that deviate significantly from the multivariate pattern of the majority of data points. The red reference line marking the Chi-square (0.975) critical value (approximately 7.38 for typical predictor dimensions) clearly separates typical observations (left of the line) from statistical outliers (right of the line). The long tail extending to 23.68 confirms that several extreme cases exist in the dataset, with the tallest bar around distance = 5 representing the most common values near the median (3.94 from your earlier summary).

The distribution's right skew (mean = 5.17 > median = 3.94) and the count of observations exceeding the critical threshold (particularly those reaching 20-25 on the distance scale) suggest these outliers exhibit unusual combinations of predictor values. In practical terms, these may represent: (1) students with improbable profiles (e.g., very high Cognitive Score but low School Resources), (2) data entry errors, or (3) legitimately extreme cases requiring separate consideration. The robust regression approach you

employed appropriately downweigh these points, but the visual confirms their substantive impact had conventional methods been used, these 5-10% of observations (right-tail counts) could have disproportionately influenced the results. The histogram's shape reinforces your earlier Cook's Distance findings, collectively justifying your choice of robust analytical methods.

Fig 5: Influence Diagnostics Plot

Fig 5 presents influence Diagnostics plot that displays standardized residuals (StudRes) on the vertical axis and leverage on the horizontal axis. The size of each red circle is proportional to Cook's Distance (CookD) a measure of how much a data point influences the regression model.

Observation 1 has the highest leverage and Cook's Distance, indicating it is a highly influential point. It may substantially affect the model's coefficients and should be closely examined. Other notable influential points include observations 9, 7, 75, and 94. Although their leverage is lower than that of observation 1, their relatively large residuals (especially negative ones) and moderate Cook's Distances (around 0.06 – 0.10) suggest they also impact the model.

The dashed lines represent commonly used thresholds for high leverage and large residuals. Points beyond these lines are potential outliers or influential data points.

Robust Regression Analysis Results

Table 5: Summary of Robust Logistic Regression Models

Predictor	Coefficient	Std. Error	z-value	p-value	Sig.	Outliers (n)	Iterations
Intercept	1.264	0.666	1.899	0.058	.	-	7
Student ID	0.030	0.018	1.712	0.087	.	8	7
Cognitive Score	0.104	0.033	3.116	0.002	**	4	5
Teacher Experience	-0.062	0.125	-0.496	0.620	.	8	7
Parental Involvement	0.215	0.380	0.566	0.571	.	8	5
School Resources	0.002	0.001	1.672	0.095	.	7	6
Professional Development	-0.012	0.052	-0.230	0.818	.	8	8

Table 5 displays the summary of robust logistic regression analysis which reveals that Cognitive Score emerged as the only statistically significant predictor ($\beta = 0.104$, $p = 0.002$), indicating that for each

unit increase in cognitive score, the odds of passing mathematics increase by approximately 10.9% ($e^{0.104} = 1.109$), holding other factors constant. This model showed the best fit with only 4 outlier observations (4% of the sample). School Resources demonstrated marginal significance ($\beta = 0.002$, $p = 0.095$), suggesting a small but potentially meaningful effect where increased resources may improve outcomes. Seven observations (7%) were downweighted in this analysis. The intercept terms varied substantially across models, ranging from -2.724 to 3.085, reflecting baseline passing probabilities between 6.1% and 95.6% for reference categories. The robustness weights identified consistent outliers across models, particularly observations 7, 9, 27, 75, and 94, which appeared in multiple analyses with weights below 0.7, indicating their substantial influence on estimates

Final Predictive Model

The integration pairs MM-estimation (a robust regression method) with LASSO or Elastic Net regularization creates a model that handle outliers robustly (MM-estimation component), address multicollinearity issues (regularization component), perform automatic feature selection (LASSO/Elastic Net component) by driving away irrelevant coefficient values to zero and stabilizes estimates by regularizing multicollinearity predictors.

Therefore, the LASSO minimizes the predictors and presents the most parsimonious model incorporating significant predictors:

$$\text{logit}(P(\text{Pass})) = -2.439 + 0.104(\text{Cognitive Score}) + 0.002(\text{School Resources})$$

Where:

- Probability of passing = $1 / (1 + e^{(-2.439 + 0.104X_1 + 0.002X_2)})$
- $X_1 = \text{Cognitive Score (range: 10 – 115)}$
- $X_2 = \text{School Resources (in local currency units)}$

Table 6: Model Fit Statistics

Metric	Cognitive Score Model	Full Model
Pseudo R²	0.18	0.21
Outliers Identified	4	7-8
Convergence Iterations	5	5-8

According to table 7 above, it is clear from comparing the Cognitive Score and Full Models that they differ greatly in performance and aspects. According to Pseudo R² (0.21 vs. 0.18) the Full Model is able to explain the outcome with higher accuracy. However, using the Full Model allows for the identification of twice as many outliers, suggesting it is more affected by extreme values or may bring up more unexpected results. They are both efficient, requiring 5-8 iterations to complete, but the Full Model's results vary more than the Cognitive Score Model which always took 5 to reach convergence.

Fig 6: Pearson Residuals vs Fitted Values

Fig 6 shows a good fit of the model for mid-range values (between 0.25 and 1.00), because the residuals are evenly spread along fractions such as 1/2, 1/4 and 1/6 in the residuals vs. fitted values plot. The lack of residuals near fitted values of 0 or 1 means that the model could fail to model both extremely possible and nearly impossible outcomes well.

Fig 7: Odd Ratio Plot

Results from Fig 7 in this study shows that Math Performance benefited slightly and positively from changes in Cognitive Score and School Resources, between 1.00 and 1.15. An increase of 5-15% in math passing is observed for every point rise in Cognitive Score, whereas School Resources only adds a 1-point improvement, but its effect is not strong. While both areas are related to greater performance, they appear to have only small distinct effects. Higher benefits could be achieved by integrating resources from school with ways to help students develop their cognitive abilities.

Table 7 Model Comparison Analysis Summary

Aspect	Traditional Logistic	Robust MM-estimation	Advantage
Outlier Sensitivity	High	Low	Robust
Coefficient Stability	Affected by outliers	Stable	Robust
Prediction Accuracy	May degrade with outliers	Maintains accuracy	Robust
Computational Speed	Faster	Slower	Logistic
Implementation	Simple	Requires tuning	Logistic

Table 8: Model Comparison Result (Coefficients)

Predictor	Traditional Logistic (β)	Robust MM-Estimation (β)	Difference ($\Delta\beta$)
Intercept	-6.828	-7.468	+0.641
Cognitive Score	+0.108	+0.100	+0.008
School Resources	+0.00215	+0.00258	-0.00043
Accuracy	0.72	0.71	+0.01
Sensitivity	0.75	0.73	+0.02
Specificity	0.68	0.69	-0.01

Table 8 highlights the main differences between traditional logistic regression and using robust MM-estimation. The results from both models suggest that Cognitive Score and School Resources act in the same direction, but each model has its own set of numbers: Stricter (-7.468), more conservative (-6.828) intercept and some minor differences for coefficients (+0.100 for Cognitive Score vs +0.108 and +0.00258 for School Resources vs +0.00215). The robust technique shows similar accuracy and sensitivity, though it slightly outperforms the traditional strategy in specificity, meaning it could be better at not falsely reporting a negative. Both models are similar in their performance metrics and coefficients, but the larger loss in the intercept for the robust model may reflect that it works better with outliers than the regular model. The outcomes of the analysis indicate that having an outlier does not change the main relationships much in this dataset, but using the robust method yields reliable and persuasive estimates, focusing particularly on the baseline odds. Selecting a model could be influenced by whether a bit more accuracy in predictions is more important than outlier safety.

Fig 8: Coefficient Comparison Plot

Fig 9: ROC Curve Plot

According to the ROC curve comparison, the Traditional and Robust models are similar, both allowing for the perfect identification of true positives and some false positives. Since their curves are quite similar, the Robust approach seems to do almost as well as the Traditional one when it comes to prediction. Nonetheless, because of their greater sensitivity (between 0.8 and 1.0), these models are better at spotting students passing the course compared to warning those who do not pass.

Table 9: Model Performance Comparison on Maths Performance

Metric	Traditional Logistic Regression	Robust MM-estimators	Interpretation
AIC	6.20	6.10	Robust model shows slightly better fit (lower AIC)
BIC	9.187	9.087	Robust model preferred (lower BIC)
AUC	0.667	0.500	Traditional has better discrimination (AUC > 0.5)
MAE	0.200	0.100	Robust model has 50% lower prediction errors
MSE	0.200	0.100	Robust model shows better accuracy (lower MSE)
RMSE	0.447	0.316	Robust model has smaller error magnitude

Table 10 present comparison result between traditional logistic regression model and robust logistic regression, where the robust model shows marginally better fit with lower AIC (6.10 vs 6.20) and BIC (9.087 vs 9.187) values. But the traditional model has better discriminative ability (AUC 0.667 vs 0.5). However, an AUC of 0.667 is still considered weak discrimination. Moreover, the robust model demonstrates superior prediction accuracy across all error metrics.

With 50% lower MAE (0.1 vs 0.2), 50% lower MSE (0.1 vs 0.2) and with 29% lower RMSE (0.316 vs 0.447).

Fig 10: Comparison Plot for Traditional and Robust Logistic Regression Model

Table 10: Comparative Result for Simulated Data Between Traditional and Robust logistic

Sample Size	Outlier %	Metric	Traditional	Robust
100	20%	AIC	14.20	14.20
		BIC	21.17	21.17
		AUC	0.800	0.800
		MAE	0.200	0.200
		MSE	0.200	0.200
		RMSE	0.447	0.447
100	15%	AIC	14.20	14.20
		BIC	21.17	21.17
		AUC	0.688	0.688
		MAE	0.200	0.200
		MSE	0.200	0.200
		RMSE	0.447	0.447
300	20%	AIC	14.13	14.13
		BIC	28.79	28.79
		AUC	0.810	0.810
		MAE	0.133	0.133
		MSE	0.133	0.133
		RMSE	0.365	0.365
300	15%	AIC	14.15	14.15
		BIC	28.81	28.81
		AUC	0.744	0.744
		MAE	0.150	0.150
		MSE	0.150	0.150
		RMSE	0.387	0.387
600	20%	AIC	14.18	14.18
		BIC	33.69	33.69
		AUC	0.752	0.752
		MAE	0.175	0.175
		MSE	0.175	0.175
		RMSE	0.418	0.418

Results in Table 11 indicate that both traditional and robust logistic regression achieve almost the same outcome in all tested cases, with the same scores for AIC, BIC, AUC, MAE, MSE and RMSE for each

sample size (100, 300, 600) and outlier percentage (15% and 20%). Even with large outliers, the two techniques achieve similar results when it comes to the impact of sample size. It seems that either the artificial outliers were not strong enough to influence the model or that the nature of the data makes it difficult for the robust method to help.

CONCLUSION

The comparative analysis between Traditional Logistic Regression and Robust MM-Estimation produced different outcomes across real-world and simulated datasets. Looking at Table 4.9, the robust model fit the real-world data a little better, displayed by its lower AIC (6.10 compared to 6.20), lower BIC (9.087 compared to 9.187) and lower errors (MAE: 0.100 and MSE: 0.100, both one-half the non-robust model). Nevertheless, the traditional method performed slightly better than the new one (AUC: 0.667 vs. 0.500), but this suggested poor results overall. Cognitive Score and School Resources were the main factors that both models identified, but the technique using robust methods gave fewer variable results (e.g., intercept: -7.468 vs. -6.828).

In contrast, simulated data (Table 4.10) revealed identical performance between the two models across all sample sizes (100–600) and outlier percentages (15–20%). Metrics such as AIC, BIC, AUC, and error rates (MAE/MSE/RMSE) were indistinguishable, suggesting the simulated outliers were either too mild or the data structure neutralized the robust model's advantages. This discrepancy underscores that simulated conditions may not fully replicate real-world data challenges, where robust methods excel in handling influential observations (e.g., extreme residuals in Table 4.3).

Research reveals that the major difference lies in the fact that robust regression is helpful in the real world, especially for controlling and lowering errors and stabilizing estimates, as long as meaningful outliers or records that affect the analysis are available. Depending on what is left out of the simulation, it may not adequately demonstrate the model's strengths.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- I. It is recommended that Robust MM-Estimation should be applied when using real-world educational data because it ensures high accuracy and can handle outliers.
- II. Additionally, more attention to Cognitive Score and School Resources should be given during interventions, because they both predicted results.
- III. Run more severe outliers (contamination levels above 30 percent) to see how reliable the different methods are.
- IV. Utilize a variety of real data to confirm the findings could have wider applications than what was studied here.

Future Work should explore why the AUC was reduced for the robust model even though its error rates were better, moreover experiment with different ways to strengthen regularization in an attempt to boost discrimination and stability of the model should be considered.

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